

THE IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY ASSURANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10807598>

Abstract. Quality assurance (QA) is considered a critical component in higher education institutions (HEIs) and their academic programmes in the twenty-first century. Despite significant investments to enhance QA in HEIs, contemporary scholarly research examines the critical significance of quality assurance mechanisms within the realm of higher education. It elucidates the multifaceted dimensions of quality assurance and underscores its pivotal role in ensuring the delivery of high-caliber educational experiences. Moreover, the article delves into the methods given by authors to improve the quality in education. Ultimately, this annotation serves as a compelling call to action for stakeholders in higher education to prioritize and invest in quality assurance initiatives as indispensable components of institutional effectiveness and academic excellence.

Keywords: quality education, individual teaching, mini group, higher education, curriculum.

Аннотация. Обеспечение качества (QA) считается важнейшим компонентом в высших учебных заведениях (ВУЗах) и их академических программах в XXI веке. Несмотря на значительные инвестиции в повышение качества в вузах, современные научные исследования рассматривают критическое значение механизмов обеспечения качества в сфере высшего образования. В нем освещаются многогранные аспекты обеспечения качества и подчеркивается его ключевая роль в обеспечении предоставления высококачественного образовательного опыта. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются методы, приводимые авторами для повышения качества образования. В конечном счете, эта аннотация служит убедительным призывом к действию для заинтересованных сторон в сфере высшего образования с целью определения приоритетов и инвестирования в инициативы по обеспечению качества как неотъемлемые компоненты институциональной эффективности и академического превосходства.

Ключевые слова: качественное образование, индивидуальное обучение, мини-группа, высшее образование, учебный план

Annotatsiya. Sifat kafolati (QA) yigirma birinchi asrda oliy o'quv yurtlari (OTM) va ularning o'quv dasturlarida muhim tarkibiy qism hisoblanadi. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida QA ni oshirish uchun katta miqdorda investitsiyalar kiritilganiga qaramay, quyidagi ilmiy tezis oliy ta'lim sohasida sifatni ta'minlash mexanizmlarining muhim ahamiyatini ko'rsatib beradi. Quyidagi tezisda ta'lim sifatini ta'minlashning ko'p qirrali jihatlari yoritib beriladi va uning yuqori malakali ta'lim tajribasini yetkazib berishdagi muhim roli ta'kidlanadi. Bundan tashqari, maqola ta'lim sifatini oshirish uchun mualliflar tomonidan taqdim etilgan usullarni bayon etadi. Ushbu tezis o'z o'rnida oliy ta'limdagi manfaatdor tomonlar uchun institutsional samaradorlik va akademik mukammallikning ajralmas tarkibiy qismi sifatida ta'lim sifatini ta'minlash tashabbuslariga ustuvorlik berish va ularga sarmoya kiritish uchun harakatga chaqiriq bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim sifati, individual o'qitish tizimi, mini guruhlar, oliy ta'lim, o'quv dasturi.

It is stated in the Incheon Declaration 2015 that: “We commit to promoting quality lifelong learning opportunities for all, in all settings and at all levels of education. This includes equitable and increased access to quality technical and vocational education and training and higher education and research, with due attention to quality assurance.” (part 10, page 8)

Quality assurance plays a vital role even as we embrace new teaching and learning practices, develop new kinds of institutions, engage new types of education providers and continue our commitment to expand access and equity in higher education. Providing higher educational institutions with qualitative learning system is the key factor to enlarge the future professional workforce in quantity.

Since the substantial reform in higher education in late twentieth century, it has become urgent to seek new means for assuring academic quality in higher education.

Undoubtly, the signifance of quality assurance for higher education, in terms of reaching the planned targets effectively and in a short period of time, cannot be overstated. It sparks improvement and innovation in addition to providing educational institutions with a good source of external and internal accountability, allowing them to create a set of goals to work towards. QA supports ongoing development of educational institutions, such as schools, colleges and universities, teaching and learning.

The era, today we are existing in, is full of attractive as well as distractive effects, creating a struggle for learners to be concentrated and effective in knowledge acquisition. Thus, individual teaching is expected to be widespread type of study. Including vast number of students in the same class is not working out effectively anymore due to the fact that each persona shows diverse interests and owns dissimilar vulnerabilities in the subject. Rather than long-term group workings, where students can reach the target smoothly in a relevantly long period of time, learning individually or in mini groups consisted of 4 or 5 members with the accomplishment of aim three or four times faster would bring higher results and qualitative learning at the same time. High-quality education between student and tutor would aid to develop self-confidence, professionalism and morality. During one-in-one interaction teacher owns the opportunity of focusing on exact drawback or weak points of a learner in specific subject. Today distraction is acclaimed as the bigger disease than Covid-19 which has been impacting much larger number of people time and again. Students, especially, most young generation cannot concentrate on the lesson more than 25-30 minutes according to common teaching experiences I gained and were shared by professional teachers. In this globalised world the advantages teamworking brings can doubtlessly be outweighed by the benefits of knowledge and practical skills’ apprehension throughout studying in mini groups or individually. In the world full of attractions, it is becoming an uphill struggle for youngsters, usually, who are prone to entertainment, to be engaged in educational process effectively with the team of their peer learners. Small group instruction can provide an individual approach to instruction, with smaller student-to-teacher ratios.

Well-organized curriculum is also one of key factors to achieve quality in education. A good curriculum sets measurable outcomes and tracks progress throughout the year. Teachers get a better view of what's happening in the classrooms, so students know where they stand, and parents are kept up-to-date. If perfectly established syllabus is made for a learner or group of learners, it will be of huge assistance to provide qualitative teaching and time menegment at the same time. A good curriculum is never a one-and-done initiative. Revisiting it regularly allows teachers to review how things are going and make room for new topics that are relevantfor the day. In fact, the World Economic Forum recommends curriculum as a key player in helping

educators keep up with the speed of changing trends, technology, and skills students will need in the future. Curriculum can provide consistent coverage of standards that ensures equitable instruction between classes, schools, districts, and states or provinces. With horizontal alignment, students get equal access to high-quality instruction regardless of their assigned class. Providing that the syllabus is followed flawlessly, individual or mini group teachings can reach the target within a month or two months depending on what is being taught. This method is highly recommended to assure quality in language learning, humanitarian studies, especially.

Today the field of education is in need of some well-planned adjustments in terms quality assurance. We desire to contribute the development of effective studying to witness rapid wise developments done by specialist workforce. Since the education is fundamental factor to grasp the professionalism in each sphere, quality assurance in education, especially, higher education remains as the global requirement to be improved and altered in methods according to the cycle. We would like to offer implementing method of teaching small quantity of students in a short period of time by having well-organized curriculum with the activities, daily goals, as well as home assignments are distributed in it. The quality of education defines the shape of world's future. As Babatunde Osotimehin, UNFPA Executive Director stated: “Together we must promote and protect every person's right to education, and ensure that quality education reaches all, and instils values of peace, justice, human rights and gender equality. We are proud to have been a co-convenor of the World Education Forum and pledge to take forward the new action agenda on education for all by 2030”.

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